

A smile between strangers: Enhancing social interaction in urban spaces

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Abstract As humans gravitate to urban centers in greater numbers, our daily reality is becoming increasingly marked by contact with strangers. There is evidence that engaging with strangers can have a positive effect on our mood; yet we tend to avoid each other, and feel alone in the crowd. What if there was a way to spark positivity among strangers in public spaces? This paper presents a design case to explore how technology can playfully disrupt daily flows by encouraging small but meaningful moments of mutual acknowledgment between strangers. We detail how two key design parameters - "connotative" and "peripheral" - were used to create a personal, body-worn prototype device intended to trigger interaction between people in public places and promote feelings of curiosity, connectedness, and happiness. We describe early findings of an original pilot study, and discuss possible future research directions and applications.

Keywords *Social interaction, Technology, Strangers, Urban, Happiness*

Introduction

Alone in the crowd

As life in congested, chaotic urban centers becomes the norm (WHO, 2016), more people are spending their days in places and amid people to whom they bear no discernible relationship. Faced with impersonal landscapes and the anonymity of crowds, it is tempting to fall back on the comfort of familiar communities, now conveniently portable within our smartphones. Anthropologist Amber Case (2015) comments that "the phone itself has more relation,

history and identity to you than an airport, for instance, or a highway. So you often find people using their phones in these kind of inhuman places in order to get back some of that humanity that's been put on pause." While reaching out to virtual stand-ins can give us a quick boost of connection, it also drains our attention away from physically present people and surroundings. In the long run, over-reliance on virtual communities may actually lead to a greater sense of alienation and loneliness: the anxious, paradoxical state that Sherry Turkle (2012) calls being "alone together".

Figure 1. In his "Public Isolation Project", San Francisco photographer Jeremy Brooks documented the many ways people isolate themselves in urban settings. (<https://www.flickr.com/photos/jeremybrooks/sets/72157625212318739/with/17673192096/>).

Figure 2. Facilitated interaction (center) can be a more accessible alternative to direct interaction (left) and ignoring each other (right).

The social potential of strangers

Modern cities have been ground zero for the “alone together” phenomenon even since before the digital era. In their portrayal of the social life of cities, writes Bearman (2005), early sociologists characterized urban social life as a sad series of “thin, episodic, instrumental, and univalent” interactions between relative strangers. Yet there is evidence that such encounters between strangers, then and now, may harbor untapped potential for generating happiness. Sandstrom (2014) found participants felt equally happy after interacting with people close to them as they did interacting with people they didn’t know well, while Epley and Schroeder (2014) found train and bus commuters who were asked to converse with a stranger reported a more positive experience commuting than those who kept to themselves, or who commuted as usual.

Despite these positive outcomes, our cultural norm against socializing with strangers (Goffman, 1967) has filled us with negative preconceptions of what such interactions might entail. To that end, we are not focusing on engaging strangers to talk to each other more often. Strangers are strangers, there are unwritten rules, consideration norms for each other, and we should respect them.

Goals

The research goal is to explore how responsive technology could be leveraged to enhance perceptions and overcome barriers to interaction between strangers. There is already evidence that the presence of an intermediary agent, such as a dog, can facilitate social interaction between humans (Figure 2). When crossing paths with a stranger accompanied by a dog, people are more likely to provide basic social acknowledgement (Messent, 1984), glance, smile, and start conversations (Mader, Hart & Bergin, 1989), and even agree to give money or go out on a date (Guéguen & Ciccotti, 2008). Strangers accompanied by dogs are also rated as more likeable (Rossbach & Wilson, 1992).

We explored more of that aspect by doing field research in different neighborhoods of San Francisco, observing and interviewing strangers that experienced some level of interaction triggered by the presence of a pet.

Based on these findings, we hypothesized that a responsive technology designed with the qualities of pet dogs on the street in mind - playful, engaging extensions of other humans - would trigger social interactions between strangers in many possible levels in positive ways. Like dogs, this technology would “nudge” strangers to look or smile at each other by acting as a safe, low-commitment precursor to the riskier, high-commitment interaction with a human. We also hypothesized that in some cases, such interactions would be accompanied by feelings of curiosity, connectedness, and happiness.

We hope to bring a fresh approach to new forms of social interactions where community-building has frayed. As real-world interactions become more and more laborious, we look into new forms of communication, beyond digital interfaces, without altering what it means to be human.

Design parameters

We explored a range of characteristics to define what constitutes an ideal social facilitator. These characteristics needed to comply with the constraints of a brief encounter between strangers in a public place, while maximizing the positive human impact.

Prior to our field research we named this social interaction as “Indirect Interaction” Inspired by indirect mutualism relations observed in nature, we named the person with a pet or a baby as “donor”, the pet or baby as “transmitter” and the strangers engaged as “recipient”. For the field research we observed and interviewed people in three different situations: waiting, recreation and transit. Within the sample size (n=10) of our interviews and sample size (n=25) observations, we found evidence of the indirect interactions. The most relevant findings for our research were:

- *People are willing to engage with a dog/baby regardless of the situation. Walking, waiting, commuting, etc. involve different social norms and the indirect interactions vary accordingly like amount of time spent or depth of interaction.*
- *Introversion is not a cause for non-interaction, people let their pets do the interaction for them. Safety concerns are the most common reason why people can be cautious about engaging in interactions with strangers.*

- *Privacy is not a concern, even with donors admitting having their characteristics expressed by the transmitter. Recipients don't seem to make any direct relation between the pet behavior the the owner's personality.*
- *The Transmitter's (babies's and dogs's) attitude definitely affects the response from recipients*

Partly following Ju and Leifer's (2008) model of "implicit interactions", which articulates the design of interactive systems filled with gestural aliveness, yet demanding less explicit input from users, and the urban observations we narrowed down to two design parameters:

1. Connotative
2. Peripheral

We define **Connotative** as the act of communicating in ways that are emotion-driven, abstract, and open to interpretation, rather than logic-driven, concrete, and specific. A playful and relatively ambiguous appearance can spark curiosity and project positive mood while leaving room for onlookers to draw their own, subjective interpretations.

We define **Peripheral** as a cognitive space where we are attuned to objects, but do not attend to specifically. Interactive objects with this quality can draw attention to themselves temporarily, but recede to the background when no longer needed. Strangers who are placed in close proximity to each other, for example in elevators and on public transportation, might appreciate the ability to easily opt in or out of the interaction.

The combination of these elements also mitigate against the technology monopolizing attention for itself, ensuring it acts instead as an enhancer of *humans'* natural talents for social meaning-making.

Figure 3. The device pictured off (left) and half-way on (right).

Prototype

Design

We designed our first exploratory prototype to be a standalone, physical object that could be embedded in everyday garments and accessories, such as scarves, hoods, and bags. Invisible when dormant, the device would glow brightly through the fabric when activated, triggering a sense of curiosity and cheer from passersby without placing undue demands on their attention (Figure 3).

In keeping with the design principles we laid out in the previous section, our prototype was designed to (1) visually **express** positivity in an intelligible but not overly specific way, and (2) to be noticeable in the **periphery** of people's perception. To satisfy (1), we chose the shape of a smiley face (two eyes and an upturned mouth surrounded by a circle). A universally recognized icon, we determined that the smiley face clearly communicated positivity without being overly abstract or overly literal or concrete (Figure 4). We solicited informal feedback on eight versions of the face, each with different arrangements and proportions of features (Figure 5), as well as options for color of the face when lit, and color of the cloth (black or white).

Figure 4.

Figure 5. Of the eight versions of the face, the version in the upper right-hand corner was chosen.

Figure 6. The device is invisible when dormant (left) A two-step trigger lights up outline and eyes (center), then the mouth (right).

To satisfy (2), we referred to Ju and Takayama's (2009) study of approachability and gesture and designed the prototype to light up incrementally, in a two-step process: first the outline and eyes of the smiley face would light up (signaling alertness), then the upturned mouth (signaling friendly recognition) (Figure 6). This instilled a more dynamic, lifelike quality to the interaction.

Execution

A shallow cylindrical case was constructed of plywood to house the LED lights, then outfitted with a circular cover laser-cut with the features of the smiley face (outline, eyes, mouth) for the LEDs to glow through. We used an Arduino to control the RGB LEDs. The LEDs were controlled by two soft buttons made of neoprene and conductive fabric: when pressed, the buttons bridged the electrical circuit, lighting the LEDs.

Pilot study

Method

As an exploratory pilot study, we employed a field experiment. We outfitted an experimenter with the prototype, a smiley face embedded in a white scarf that was invisible unless activated (lit up). We used a Wizard of Oz technique (Dahlback, 1993) to give the illusion that the prototype operated spontaneously; in reality, the experimenter was instructed to activate the prototype whenever he was in an immediate passerby's line of sight. Two other researchers walked behind the experimenter and noted the incidence of gazes and smiles directed at the experimenter. If a passerby clearly reacted to the prototype being activated, one of the researchers approached the passerby and solicited feedback.

The primary interests of the pilot study were to gather informal, qualitative feedback on (1) how people interact with the prototype and wearer, (2) how they interpret the behavior of the prototype, and (3) what feelings, if any, they had towards the wearer. This pilot

Figure 7. Front view (left), view with cover removed (center), rear view (right).

Figure 8. Two passersby gaze and smile at the prototype as we stroll down San Francisco's busy waterfront promenade.

was carried out in a selection of downtown San Francisco locations. We estimate that we observed about 200 people cross paths with the wearer, and got feedback from about 30 people.

Findings

Findings from our pilot research were preliminary but provocative. In terms of (1), we noted that the prototype attracted a moderate amount of attention. We were surprised by the relatively low incidence of smiling overall in response to the prototype. A few people waved, pointed the prototype out to their companions, gave us a thumbs up, or struck up conversations.

In terms of (2), passersby did not seem to attribute motivation to the prototype, or make inferences about how it worked. People were more likely to think it was

purely decorative and particular to specific sub-communities.

In terms of (3), few passersby reported impressions of the wearer: some didn't notice him, while others remarked on his physical features (young, male, Asian).

Based on the responses we noticed that most of the reactions were probably due to the unexpected ludic aspect of the prototype. Inspired by David Rose's (2014) theory of enchanted objects we hypothesize that by "enchanted" daily objects with technology using characteristics of fairy tales and science we may create the positive impression not just an unexpected playful device.

Figure 9. MUNI underground train station.

Figure 10. San Francisco Ferry Building.

Implications

We propose that thoughtfully designed technology can help facilitate such encounters, and hope our exploration of such technology will promote discussion around how to design for positive social encounters in modern cities.

To test the efficacy of variations in the prototype's physical design and interaction style, we plan to conduct follow-up studies with a more abstract design, and potentially introduce other sensorial inputs like sound. We are especially keen to deepen our understanding of how to design for "connotative" and "peripheral" qualities in a way that encourages people to be socially exploratory, while respecting their need for privacy and peace of mind. Future iterations may build in "intelligence"; however, limited intelligence based on animal cognition or some other limited capacity to serve as a catalyst for humans to be social and creative, drawing their own conclusions and crafting their own stories.

Possible applications include "enchanted" daily garments and accessories (e.g., bags, bottles, clothes, jewelry), architecture and urban design, mobility spaces (e.g., subways, bus stops, sidewalks), and transportation (e.g., bicycles, cars, skateboards).

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